

Chemical Knowledge of the Hindus of Old.¹

BY

SIR PRAFULLA CHANDRA RAY, C.I.E., D.Sc., Ph.D.,

President, Indian Chemical Society.

An eminent Belgian Indologist, Goblet d'Alviella, has very justly observed that India is a land of paradoxes, that whatever is of ancient origin excites our admiration—her literature including her unrivalled dramas, her transcendental philosophy of the *Upanishads* and the *Geeta* attracted the attention of the West long ago. India was once the cradle of mathematical sciences including arithmetic and algebra; the system of notation, popularly ascribed to the Arabs, is really the product of the Hindu brain.

Max Müller says somewhere that if India had presented no other gift to Europe than that of the numerals, the debt of the latter to the former would have been unrequitable.² Ancient Assyria, Babylon and

¹ Inaugural address delivered by the President, Indian Chemical Society, at its first annual General Meeting held at the chemistry lecture theatre, Hindu University, Benares.

² The learned Professor of Sanskrit of Oxford University says "In science too, the debt of Europe to India has been considerable. There is, in the first place, the great fact that the Indians invented the numerical figures used all over the world. The influence which the decimal system of reckoning dependent on those figures has had not only on mathematics, but on the progress of civilisation in general, can hardly be overestimated. During the 8th and 9th centuries the Indians became the teachers in arithmetic and algebra of the Arabs and through them of the nations of the West. Thus, though we call the latter science by an Arabic name, it is a gift we owe to India."—Macdonnell's *History of Sanskrit Literature*, p. 424.

Egypt exist only in their monuments, cuneiform inscriptions or hieroglyphs, inscribed on slabs of stone or baked clay. The recent discoveries in Tutankhamen mausoleum have yielded many new specimens of Egyptian art of all kinds. Rome and Greece live in their literature and philosophy, but the Hindu nation persists to-day as she did 2,500 years ago, when Gautama Buddha preached at Benares, the sacred city where we are holding our meeting to-day. Sakya Muni knew that if he could make a breach in the citadel of Hindu religion and culture, the whole of India would readily embrace his new doctrine. For a time Brahminical supremacy must have been shaken to its foundation as is proved by the archæological findings of Sarnath now some five miles from this city. But the tenacious vitality of the Hindu religion is something marvellous and it struck sagacious tourists and observers like Pierre Loti. Even to-day European visitors who find the pious Hindu performing his daily religious practices and ablutions at the bathing ghats of the Ganges can have but little difficulty in coming to the conclusion that impact with the West has scarcely produced any effect on the Hindu. He pursues his daily even tenor of life as his ancestors did twenty-five centuries ago. No wonder that the poet should exclaim :—

“ The East bowed low before the blast
 In patient, deep disdain,
 She let the legions thunder past
 And plunged in thought again.”

No doubt the Hindus have been meditating—ever lost in abstruse metaphysical subtleties, but, all the same, in ancient India physical science found her votaries. I have barely time to allude to the atomic theory as propounded

in the Vaiseshika System of Kanāda, which anticipates the doctrine of Anaxagoras, Empedocles, etc. I shall limit myself this afternoon to the keen powers of observation as also the necessity of experimental methods enjoined by the Hindus of old, so far as chemical processes are concerned. Indeed, Dhundukanātha, the author of the standard iatro-chemical treatise *Rasendra Chintamani*, (lit. gems of mineral preparations), says—"They are alone to be regarded as real teachers who can show by experiment what they teach. They are the deserving pupils, who, having learnt the experiments from their teachers can actually perform them. The rest, both the teachers and the pupils, are merely stage-actors."

This author, again, acknowledges his indebtedness to the standard work on the subject, *Rasārṇava*, in which occurs an elaborate account of the processes of sublimation, distillation, etc., as also of the apparatus required for the process. Indian alchemists are also eloquent in their veneration for and indebtedness to the great adept, Nagārjuna, to whom is ascribed the invention of the above processes. One instance will suffice to give you an idea of the methods adopted for the purification of mercury.

मिथिली चेद्वसे नागवङ्गौ विक्रयहेतुना ।

ताभ्यां स्यात् क्वत्रिमो दोषः तस्मृक्तिः पातनद्रव्यात् ।

१ अश्लीषं चतुर्विधं सुखादपक्कं
 बाष्पेणु खिलमङ्गलं न तस्मिन्बानि ।
 वत् शर्मं व्यरचयमयती गुरुणा
 श्रीदामां तद्विद्धं वदानि वीतमङ्कः ॥
 चक्ष्मापयन्ति यदि द्वायवितुं चमले
 दूतेन्द्र शर्मगुरुवी गुरुवत् एव ।
 त्रिभ्यास्त एव तथयन्ति गुरोः पुरी वे
 शेषाः पुनश्चादमयाभिषयं भजन्ते ॥

The above, literally rendered, runs as follows:—
 “Fraudulent dealers adulterate (alloy) mercury with lead and tin, hence these impurities are to be removed by subjecting the mercury to triple distillation.”

The identification of metals by the colouration of their flames is referred to in *Rasārṇava*—

“Copper yields a blue flame, that of the tin is pigeon-coloured, that of the lead is pale tinted¹..... .”

We are not aware of similar tests being applied anywhere at such an early period as a qualitative test for metals.² As regards the high degree of skill in metallurgy attained by the Hindus, it is enough to mention the iron pillar near Delhi.³ In the ancient Hindu literature only six metals are mentioned, *viz.*, gold, silver, iron, lead, tin and copper. The name of a seventh metal—zinc—occurs in European history for the first time in the works of Paracelsus, who leaves us in the dark as to the nature of his “zincken,” which he designates as “semi” or bastard metal.

Libavius was the first to mention the properties of zinc more exactly although he was not aware that the

¹ Cf. “Lead compounds impart a pale tint to the non-luminous gas flame.”—Roscoe and Schorlemmer's Chemistry, Ed. 1879.

² Cardan (1501-1576) is perhaps the earliest to notice that the colour of the flame varies with different metals—Hoefer's *Hist. d. Chim.* Vol., II, p. 95. Ed. 1869.

³ Taking A.D. 400 as a mean date—and it certainly is not far from the truth—it opens our eyes to an unsuspected state of affairs to find the Hindus at the age capable of forging a bar of iron larger than any that had been forged even in Europe up to a very late date. As we find them, however, a few centuries afterwards using bars as long as this lat in roofing the porch of the temple at Kanarno, we must now believe that they were much more familiar with the use of this metal than they afterwards became. It is almost equally startling to find that, after exposure to wind and rain for fourteen centuries, it is unruined, and the capital and inscription are as clear and as sharp now as when put up fourteen centuries ago.”

“There is no mistake about the pillar being of pure iron. General Cunningham had a bit analysed in India by Dr. Murray and another portion was analysed in the School of Mines here by Dr. Percy. Both found it pure malleable iron without any alloy.”—Ferguson's “*History of Indian and Eastern Architecture*, Ed. 1869, p. 508.

Even now forged masses of such size are exceptional.

metal was derived from the ore known as 'calamine.' He states that "a peculiar kind of tin is found in the East Indies, called 'calaēm.' Some of this was brought to Holland, evidently by the Dutch East India Company, and came into his hands." The extraction of zinc from the ore (calamine) can be followed in every detail from the account left to us in *Rasārṇava* and specially *Rasaratnasamuchchaya*. The process as given in the latter work is reproduced below. The literal rendering of it runs thus :

"Rub calamine with turmeric, the chebulic myrabolans, resin, the salts, soot, borax¹..... Fill the inside of a crucible with the above mixture and dry it in the sun. Close its mouth with a perforated saucer. A vessel filled with water is embedded in the ground, over which the above vessel charged with the mixture is inverted, which is again heated as shown in the figure, by means of a charcoal fire. The operation is stopped when the *flame issuing from the mass changes from blue to white*. The essence of the metal, which drops into the water and has the lustre of tin, is to be collected." Indeed, the process, so elaborately given above, might be quoted almost *verbatim* in any treatise on modern chemistry.² It is practically the same as *distillatio per descensum*—the flame of a bluish tint issuing from the mouth of the crucible indicates the combustion of carbon monoxide so often observed in metallurgical operations.

¹ It is scarcely necessary to point out that highly carbonaceous substances like resin, turmeric, etc., being heated in the absence of air yield carbon in a fine state of division.

² Cf. "A mixture of two parts of ground roasted ore and one part of coal-dust is brought into the retorts, each holding about 40 pounds of the mixture. As soon as the temperature has risen high enough, the reduction begins and carbon monoxide is evolved and burns from the end of the clay adapter with a blue flame." (The italics are ours)—Roscoe and Schorlemmer's Chemistry, Ed. 1879, Vol. II, Part I, p. 225.

It is not, of course, claimed that the ancient Hindus knew that the blue colour was due to the combustion of carbon monoxide, but what I should like to lay particular stress upon is the power of keen observation underlying the description.

The ancient Hindus knew the distinction between potassium carbonate and sodium carbonate—the former is called *yavakshāra* (*lit.* ash from the spikes of barley), and the latter *sarjikakshāra*, (equivalent to *natron* from Egypt). The earliest record of this is to be found in the old Hindu work, the *Susruta*. The *Charaka* and the *Susruta* are the two standard and authoritative treatises on *Ayurveda* (*lit.* science of life). The *Charaka* is more concerned with medicine, while the *Susruta* relates more or less to surgery. Here we have a drop of 2,000 years from the *Susruta* to the remarkable discoveries of Joseph Black. In the *Susruta* the two modifications of alkali are referred to as *tikshnakshāra* (*tikshna*, *i.e.*, sharp or caustic; *kshāra*, *i.e.*, alkali), and *mridukshāra* (*i.e.*, mild alkali). The distinction between the two is quite clear. In the days of my boyhood the ashes of the plantain tree (*Musa sapientum*) were used by washermen for cleaning clothes. The reason is that it is very rich in potassium carbonate. In the *Susruta* we have many land plants mentioned which have been botanically classified in Uday Chand Dutt's *Materia Medica of the Hindus*. The *Susruta* says "on an auspicious day cut the plant down, burn it and boil the ashes with water in an iron pan and then filter through cloth folded several times." This, says the *Susruta*, is *mridukshāra*. You know what actually takes place in this process. The clean solution that is obtained is rich in potassium carbonate and is termed mild alkali.

Next comes the description of the preparation of caustic alkali, and this is the most scientific portion.

“Collect several kinds of limestone and shells and burn them strongly and add water to the resulting product. Next mix this slaked lime with the lixiviated liquid obtained above and boil and stir with an iron ladle.” The reactions that take place here can be represented in the modern way by the following equations :

This method, you will look for in vain in any European treatise before the 16th or the 17th century. The process as given in the *Susruta* is so scientific that it can be bodily transferred to any modern text-book on chemistry. Besides recommending the use of an iron vessel for boiling the liquid, the book further says that the *kshāra* so obtained, must be stored in an iron vessel with its mouth closed :

आयस्ये कुम्भे संवृतमुखे निदध्यात् ।

The *Susruta* cannot, of course, be credited with having known that carbon dioxide was to be excluded from the vessel to prevent the caustic solution from being acted upon. But the physicians of those days must have certainly realised by empirical methods that the causticity would be diminished if these precautions are not taken. Even to-day we keep caustic potash, either in iron or silver vessels. The points to be noted here are that the *Susruta* gives not only a very accurate method of preparation and preservation of the two kinds of alkali but also the distinction between the two varieties, *tikshnakshāra* and *mridukshāra*, is clearly

recognised. Davy isolated potassium and he says, "The ancients did not know how to distinguish between potassium carbonate and sodium carbonate." But in our *Ayurveda* this sharp distinction has been clearly stated.

Between the *Susruta* and Joseph Black lies a gap of some 2,000 years. Black was an M.D. of Edinburgh. In his Doctorate thesis (presented in 1755) he gave for the first time the scientific explanation of the difference between caustic and mild alkalis. He heated magnesium carbonate using the balance at each stage of the experiment, and pointed out that on strong heating there was a loss in weight. He also pointed out that a gas was given out which was called "fixed air." Ramsay in his *Life of Black* says "Quicklime is formed by heating lime-stone in the fire; it thereby acquires its burning properties or causticity." Black's essay was an epoch-making one.

M. Berthelot, under whose inspiration I took to writing my *History of Hindu Chemistry*, in reviewing my book says of this portion "that the Hindus possibly got their knowledge of this method from the Portuguese." (*Journal des Savants*, Jan. 1903, p. 34.) But against that I may point out that Chakrapāni, who was the court physician of Nayapāla (1050 A.D.), King of Gour, in the treatise which goes by his name, quotes this mode of preparation verbatim from the *Susruta*. A much older treatise, the *Vagbhata* also does the same. In the course of my studies, I came across a remarkable passage in a Buddhist work which dates as far back as 140 B.C.—I mean the *Milinda Panho*. Professor Rhys Davids translates the portion as follows: "And when the inflammation had gone down and the wound had become sweet, suppose he were then to cut into it with a lancet, and burn it with caustic. And when he had

cauterized it, suppose he were to prescribe an alkaline wash..... Now tell me, O King! would it be out of cruelty that the surgeon..... thus cut with the lancet and cauterized with the stick of caustic.”¹

It must be admitted on the other hand that the discovery of Black was quite independent and he showed that the difference between the mild and the caustic alkalis was due to the presence of carbon dioxide in the former. The *Susruta*, of course, does not say anything of this kind.

The use of metallic preparations mentioned in the Hindu Pharmacopœia also dates from a very early period. In Europe Paracelsus was, as we have said, the first to introduce metallic preparations into medicine. But in India, Vrindā who preceded Chakrapāni by at least a century and therefore must have flourished about the 9th Century A.D., or even earlier, was the first to prescribe ‘Kajjvali’ (black sulphide of mercury) as a medicine. Chakrapāni gives an elaborate description of the process of making ‘Kajjvali’. In Europe this preparation was not known before the 17th century.²

I need not proceed further. The knowledge of pharmacy which the Arabs brought to Europe was derived from the Hindus. *Ex oriente lux*. I shall conclude with the apposite words of that illustrious French Chemist, Jean Baptiste André Dumas: “What an awakening for Europe! After two thousand years she found herself again in the position to which she had been raised by the profound intellect of India and the

¹ *Sacred Books of the East*—Vol. XXXV, p. 168.

² Das Schwarze Schwefelquecksilber lehrte zuerst Turquet de Mayerne, im Anfange des 17. Jahrhunderts, durch Zusammenreiben von warmen Quecksilber mit geschmolzenem Schwefel darstellen.—Kopp: *Gesch. d. Chem.* Vol. IV, 188.

acute genius of Greece." (The first *Faraday Lecture* delivered before the Chemical Society, June 17, 1869).¹

BIBLIOGRAPHY :

P. C. RAY's *History of Hindu Chemistry*.

Calcutta, *Chuckerberty Chatterjee & Co.*
London, *Probsthain & Co.*

¹ Hoefer in his admirable *Histoire de la Chimie* also expresses the same view "L'Inde est le berceau de la filiation des peuples qui marchent à la tête de la civilisation."—Vol. I, Ed. 1866.

Apparatus for sublimation and
distillatio per descensum.

A modern method of
extraction of zinc.

The iron pillar and the
Katab minar near Delhi.

Fumigating
apparatus

Extraction of zinc
from calamine.

Apparatus for
distillation

Apparatus for extraction
of mercury from cinnabar

